

STADIEM

STARTUP DRIVEN INNOVATION IN EUROPEAN MEDIA

D4.1 MATCH AND DEVELOP PHASES REPORT - THE 1ST CYCLE

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Abstract	This document covers the activities related to the Match phase and Develop phase of the STADIEM Acceleration Programme in the first cycle, with the participation of the selected start-ups/scale-ups in Open Call 1. The report also covers the organization of the 1st kick-off joint Hubs' event in the 1st Match Phase.
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* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable covers the activities related to the Match phase and Develop phase of the STADIEM Acceleration Programme in the first cycle, with the participation of the selected start-ups/scale-ups in Open Call 1.

Following the selection of start-ups/scale-ups in Open Call 1, the STADIEM programme was initiated with the first phase of the programme; the Match Phase. 41 beneficiaries were selected and accepted the invitation to join the 1st Match phase of the STADIEM programme. The Match Phase started off mid-May 2021 with a joint Kick-off event for the 1st open call to celebrate the start of the programme. The goal of the kick-off event was to introduce the STADIEM Framework, the hubs, the start-ups/scale-ups, as well as give more information about the Match Phase and serve as an activity toward community building.

Even with the ongoing Covid-19 crisis, the consortium managed to implement the Match phase successfully as a digital framework. All of the planned events and activities were organized and executed digitally, even the STADIEM Tour & Market Study was managed completely remote.

Out of the 41 start-ups/scale-ups that were accepted to the Match phase, a total of 37 start-ups/scale-ups managed to sign LOIs with relevant corporate partners throughout Europe, while all of the start-ups/scale-ups managed to generate new leads during the Match phase. Some start-ups/scale-ups even managed to secure LOIs with several corporate partners, and all the 37 start-ups/scale-ups with LOIs applied to proceed to the Develop phase. The final evaluation of the Phase was executed mid-August 2021 at the Investment Committee meeting, where 16 start-ups/scale-ups were selected to proceed to the Develop Phase.

The Develop Phase is the second phase of the STADIEM programme, The Phase was kicked off with an onboarding meeting late-August 2021, with the final evaluation taking place during the ICM in the first week of March 2022. The Develop Phase's main KPI was the selection of at least 16 start-ups/scale-ups to start the Phase, and the readiness of at least 12 start-ups/scale-ups for the Integrate Phase. The first KPI was met, and the second KPI was also met when in early March the 12 top-performing start-ups/scale-ups were invited to join the Integrate Phase after the ICM and accepted the invitation.

To bring the lessons learned from the 1st Match phase into action, we have recognized several improvement measures to implement for the 2nd Match Phase. In the upcoming Match phase, we have scheduled an earlier start, by starting in the very beginning of May 2022. In addition, it is decided to compress the phase down to the original two months, to finish the matchmaking before the summer holidays. For the 2nd cycle, the rotation system will be changed in order to provide the best possible matches from all hubs' ecosystems, and the evaluation and selection process to refine the current process.

The STADIEM programme was devised to consist of mainly in-person activities. Due to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, the majority of all Develop Phase activities in the 1st cycle have been executed successfully online. In this report we have included some preliminary learnings from the ongoing Develop Phase for the 1st cycle, including: joint hub events seem to have greater impact, we need to facilitate investor leads better when necessary, and the project could benefit from more feedback loops with the corporate. A full evaluation of the Develop Phase and implementation of improvements for the 2nd cycle is planned in March 2022, after concluding the Develop Phase of the 1st cycle.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AB	Advisory Board
IC	Investment Committee
LOI	Letter of Intent
WP	Work package

1 INTRODUCTION

This report, D4.1 Match and Develop phases report - the 1st cycle, covers the activities related to the Match phase and Develop phase of the STADIEM Acceleration Programme in the first cycle, with the participation of the selected start-ups/scale-ups in Open Call 1. The report also covers the organization of the 1st kick-off joint Hubs' event in the 1st Match Phase. It does so by firstly presenting the Match Phase and kick-off event, followed by the Develop Phase.

The Match and Develop Phase are the two first phases in the STADIEM programme (WP4), being Task 4.1 Match and Task 4.2 Develop. The next two phases of the programme, and also the next two Tasks in WP4 is the Integrate Phase and Pilot Phase, to be covered in the D4.2 *Integration, piloting phases and assessment report - the 1st cycle* due in M23. The overall goal of WP4 STADIEM programme is to deliver the programme that has been developed in WP2 STADIEM incubation and acceleration framework, following the selection of startups in WP3 Engaging Startups/SMEs. More specifically, the objective of WP4 is to deliver the programme in four phases, consequently Match, Develop, Integrate and Pilot Phases, and the evaluation phase.

Starting off the report, there is provided a description and the objectives of the Match Phase. Secondly, there's a thorough presentation of the Match Phase Framework for the 1st cycle, including an overview of the timeline of the Phase, a description of the kick-off event to celebrate the opening of the programme for the 1st cycle, an explanation of the STADIEM Tour and Market Study including its activities, an overview of the training and upskilling activities, and finishing off with its two-step evaluation and selection process.

After the presentation of the Match Phase framework, there's a walkthrough of the budget and reimbursement in the Match Phase for the 1st cycle, the KPIs and results, deviations and corrective actions, and lastly the learnings from the 1st cycle and how to improve it for the 2nd cycle.

For the Develop Phase section of this document, we start with a description and objectives of the phase, followed by the framework. The framework includes an overview of the timeline of the 1st Develop Phase, the support activities performed by the innovation hubs, planned and organised networking and showcasing events, upskilling and training activities, and lastly the three-part evaluation and selection process of the Phase.

As with the Match Phase, the Develop Phase framework is followed by a walkthrough of the budget and reimbursement in the Develop Phase for the 1st cycle, the KPIs and results, deviations and corrective actions, and lastly the learnings from the 1st cycle and how to improve it for the 2nd cycle.

2 MATCH PHASE

TABLE 1: OVERVIEW MATCH PHASE DETAILS

Task N°	Title	Lead	Contributing Partners	Timing
4.1	Match	NMA	STK, MCB, VRT	M9-M21

2.1 DESCRIPTIONS AND OBJECTIVES

Following the selection of at least 40 start-ups/scale-ups in Open Call 1, the STADIEM programme was initiated with the first phase of the programme; the Match Phase, where the selected start-ups/scale-ups were invited to participate. The objective of this phase is as stated in the Grant Agreement, Annex 1 (page. 22), to “Identify corporate partners through the Inspirational and Market Study Tour”. The main outcome of the phase is for the start-ups/scale-ups to connect to the relevant stakeholders within each of the four hubs to secure their corporate partner(s), while acquiring knowledge about local ecosystems through the STADIEM Tour & Market Study.

In the Match phase there are to be at least 40 beneficiaries (start-ups/scale-ups), where each beneficiary can receive a maximum of € 7.000 to cover travel costs. In the 1st cycle, 41 start-ups/scale-ups were selected and invited to join the Match phase.

The Match phase is intended to be a two-month phase but was prolonged to three months for the 1st cycle. The phase had its kick-off on 19 May 2021, and the final evaluation was on 17 August 2021 at the Investment Committee meeting.

2.2 FRAMEWORK

2.2.1 Overview of the timeline

The Match Phase started off with a joint kick-off meeting, followed by a meeting with an introduction to the four innovation hubs: VRT, Storytek/Exit Academy (ST), Media City Bergen (MCB), and Next Media Accelerator (NMA). In the first round of the matchmaking through the STADIEM Tour & Market Study (2 weeks) the start-ups/scale-ups meet their main contact point hub (“mother hub”). Each mother hub was responsible for the 10 -12 start-ups/scale-ups that fit best to their ecosystem and partners. Each hub created an individual programme with activities and meetings to raise sufficient interest and buy-in. After the first round all start-ups/scale-ups move in a rotation system from hub to hub for one week at each partner.

The second part of the 1st Match phase was dedicated for the start-ups/scale-ups to finalize their matchmaking process in order to sign a Letter of Intent (LOI) with at least one corporate partner. At the end of the Match Phase the participants had to apply formally for the Develop Phase with an application form. 16 teams are selected to proceed to the Develop phase by external and internal evaluators in a two-step selection process. First, external evaluators

assess the application and select the best 25 to proceed to the Investment Committee, where the four innovation hubs and three advisory board members after a pitch session select the 16 highest-ranking start-ups/scale-ups to invite to Develop.

TABLE 2: OVERVIEW OF MATCH PHASE FRAMEWORK ACTIVITIES - 1ST CYCLE

Date	Activity
19 May 2021	Welcome Meeting (Kick-off event)
27 May 2021	Hub Intro Meeting
31 May- 01 July	Hub Rotation Period
01 July 2021	Mid-term Review (internal IHB)
04- 31 July 2021	Finalizing Matches Period
31 July	Deadline applications
01 - 15 August 2021	External evaluation
17 August 2021	Investment Committee Meeting

TABLE 3: TIMELINE OF THE MATCH PHASE ACTIVITIES - 1ST CYCLE

2021	19/5/21	31/5-13/6	14-20/6	21-27/6	26/6-4/7	5/7 - 31/7	1-17/8
MCB cohort	Kick off	MCB	VRT	ST	NMA	LOI / application	Selection
NMA cohort	Kick off	NMA	MCB	VRT	ST	LOI / application	Selection
ST cohort	Kick off	ST	NMA	MCB	VRT	LOI / application	Selection
VRT cohort	Kick off	VRT	ST	NMA	MCB	LOI / application	Selection

2.2.2 1st Kick-off Joint Hubs' Event & Intro to the Hubs

The Match Phase started off on 19 May 2021 with a joint Kick-off event for the 1st open call to celebrate the start of the programme. The event was co-organised by NMA and MCB. The goal of the kick-off event was to introduce the STADIEM Framework, the hubs, the start-ups/scale-ups, as well as give more information about the Match Phase and serve as an activity toward community building.

The kick-off event was a two-hour online event, hosted at Media City Bergen in a virtual studio production. The event was produced by Kulturoperatørene, a Norwegian full-service event company, and hosted by Arne Møller, a professional Norwegian host and speaking coach. Starting off the event was Mike Matton (VRT), welcoming the start-ups/scale-ups to the programme, and giving them a short introduction to the programme framework. Matton was followed by Dr. Tanja Deuerling (NMA), explaining the activities during the Match Phase. Each of the hubs then gave a short presentation of their hub, followed by pre-recorded and live introductions from each of the start-ups/scale-ups allocated to the specific hub. The videos from the start-ups/scale-ups were collected through a campaign on the Klipworks platform, one of the start-ups selected for the Match Phase. After the hub and start-up/scale-up introductions, the rest of the consortium partners gave a short presentation of themselves: Martel Innovate, F6S, and EBU.

After all parties had introduced themselves and their company, the start-ups/scale-ups could ask their questions for the Phase and the programme in a Q&A session for all participants. As part of the community building in the programme, the Q&A was followed by a break-out room session, where all hubs and their start-ups/scale-ups were placed in different rooms to chat and get to know each other better.

During the event, one representative from each innovation hub scored the introductions from the start-ups/scale-ups. The top-scoring introduction was announced at the very end of the event for their outstanding presentation. The winning team was awarded a t-shirt, cap, and lanyard with their company logo.

On 27 May 2021, one week after the kick-off meeting, NMA organised an online "Intro to the hubs" meeting. The goal of this meeting was for the start-ups/scale-ups to learn more about each of the innovation hubs. After welcoming the participants and recapping the Match Phase rotation system, each hub (NMA, VRT, MCB, ST) was allocated a 15-minute slot to give a more in-depth presentation of their hub. The event concluded with a presentation of the STADIEM Advisory Board.

2.2.3 STADIEM Tour and Market Study

The STADIEM Tour & Market Study was initially planned as a physical tour, where the start-ups/scale-ups would be divided into four cohorts to travel to visit each of the innovation hubs (VRT, STK, MCB & NMA) and get to know their local media and tech ecosystem. Due to the travel restrictions during the Covid-19 pandemic, the consortium decided to make the Tour & Market Study virtual.

The five-week STADIEM Tour & Market Study for the 1st cycle started on 31 May 2021. The start-ups/scale-ups started the tour by spending two weeks at the innovation hub that the hubs considered the best fit for each start-up/scale-up and their project, also called their mother hub. In the three subsequent weeks, the batches of start-ups/scale-ups rotated one week at each of the three other hubs.

TABLE 4: TIMELINE OVER THE STADIEM TOUR & MARKET STUDY HUB ROTATION - 1ST CYCLE

2021	31/5-13/6	14-20/6	21-27/6	26/6-4/7
MCB cohort	MCB	VRT	ST	NMA
NMA cohort	NMA	MCB	VRT	ST
ST cohort	ST	NMA	MCB	VRT
VRT cohort	VRT	ST	NMA	MCB

The innovation hubs decided that during the STADIEM Tour & Market Study, each hub would organize their own schedule and deploy their own methods and activities:

- **MCB** organized individual meetings with each of the start-ups/scale-ups to uncover their needs and wants in a corporate partner, provided individual opportunity spotting, and direct introduction to corporates and investors. They also organized pitching events for each batch, where they invited selected stakeholders in their ecosystem. Furthermore, MCB invited the teams to attend their annual tech conference MCB Tech .21 and their event Tech Talks.
- **VRT** organized power pitches subdivided into thematic groups with media organizations and corporates from the Sandbox Hubs. Furthermore, VRT organized demo days dedicated to technology assessments against the state of art.
- **NMA** focused on individual opportunity spotting, consulting and direct introduction to NMA partners, investors and the German media industry. Furthermore, NMA invited all teams to join the big Virtual Media Match to get in contact with the ecosystem.
- **ST/EA** offered a wide range of training sessions with focus on sales and acquisition and also offered individual opportunity spotting and introductions.

The chosen activities were based on the hubs' previous experiences on how to best engage their network and other assets, in order to help the start-ups/scale-ups to achieve the objective of the phase and identify potential corporate partners.

2.2.4 Upskilling and Training

During the duration of the Match phase, all start-ups/scale-ups had the opportunity to participate in need-based training and upskilling activities as part of the STADIEM programme. In addition to the free training sessions provided by Storytek and the Exit Academy, each start-up/scale-up was allowed a financial contribution of 4.000 € to be reimbursed for training and upskilling activities completed in the Match Phase. The training sessions, workshops and coaching had to be estimated as relevant to the project execution and pre-approved by each start-up/scale-up's mother hub.

Not all start-ups/scale-ups decided to seize the opportunity to be reimbursed for upskilling activities in the 1st Match phase. Only 18 of the 41 start-ups/scale-ups engaged in reimbursable and pre-approved upskilling activities.

Some examples of upskilling activities the start-ups/scale-ups completed in the 1st Match phase:

- ➔ Communication coaching
- ➔ Sales workshop
- ➔ Sales training and mentoring
- ➔ AI workshop
- ➔ Product market fit workshop
- ➔ VAT training
- ➔ Custom IP rights and strategies upskilling
- ➔ Legal coaching

2.2.5 Evaluation and Selection Process

During the Match Phase, the following requirements should be fulfilled by each Start-Up/Scale-Up:

- ➔ Budget for funding/upskilling in the Phase
- ➔ Start-Up/Scale-Ups presents a strategy for qualifying leads
- ➔ Start/up/scale-up presents a needs, objectives and action plan at the end of the Phase upon which they will be assessed for the evaluation to the next Phase, along with a pitch to the Investment Committee
- ➔ Corporates evaluate the Start-Up/Scale-Ups leads (max. five questions) in the needs, objectives and action plan at the end of the Phase
- ➔ Start-Up/Scale-Ups that manage to secure an LOI or equivalent will be scored higher at the end of the Phase

The Match Phase evaluation and selection process was a two-step process, consisting of:

1. 31 July - 15 August 2021: Start-ups/scale-ups submitted their application by 31 July 2022, evaluated and scored by external experts
2. 17 August 2021: The Investment Committee meeting and selection of the 16 to proceed to Develop

The start-ups/scale-ups that wished to be considered to proceed to the Develop phase, had to submit an application via an Airtable form, by 31 July 2021. The application consisted of a project proposal and a questionnaire (see Appendix A) for them to fill out. One start-up/scale-up withdrew their participation during the Match phase. Out of the remaining 40 start-ups/scale-ups, 37 of them succeeded in signing one or more letters of intent with corporate partners, all of which submitted their application before the deadline.

The first evaluation step of the Match phase was performed by independent experts. Each of the 37 applicants were assigned to the experts, with two experts evaluating each start-

up/scale-up. These expert evaluators rated and scored all applications, delivering their results to the STADIEM consortium on 15 August 2021.

Based on the average ranking resulting from the independent evaluation, the top 25 highest-scoring start-ups/scale-ups were invited to the second step of the evaluation and selection process; a pitching session for the STADIEM Investment Committee on 17 August 2021. The STADIEM Investment Committee consists of three external experts recruited from the STADIEM Advisory Board, in addition to one representative from each innovation hub. Each start-up/scale-up was allocated a slot of five minutes to pitch their proposal for the Develop phase.

Each Investment Committee member scored each of the start-ups/scale-ups' pitches on the following five criteria:

1. Objectives and ambition
2. Pathway to impact
3. Implementation (budget)
4. Corporate assessment and proof of intent
5. Motivation and clarity

Each criterion was scored between 1 and 5, where a score of 1 equal fail, and a score of 5 equals excellent. A final ranking was compiled with the average score for each start-up/scale-up, the top 16 highest-scoring start-ups/scale-ups were then selected to proceed to the Develop Phase, all of which accepted this invitation.

2.3 BUDGET AND REIMBURSEMENT

During the Match phase 1st cycle, it was originally budgeted that each of 40+ beneficiaries invited to the phase could receive a maximum of € 7.000, resulting in a total budget of € 280.000 as Third-Party Support Funding in this phase. The € 280.000 was earmarked as travel reimbursements to the beneficiaries. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic and measures taken by national governments, travel was restricted, and all Match phase activities had to be executed remotely. Therefore, the consortium agreed that the start-ups/scale-ups would rather be, as previously stated, allowed a financial contribution of 4.000 € to be reimbursed for necessary training and upskilling activities completed in the Match Phase.

With the costs of the activities from the 18 start-ups/scale-ups that accepted this invitation, a total of € 56.180 of the Third-Party Support Funding was spent by the start-ups/scale-ups on approved activities and reimbursed by the STADIEM consortium.

TABLE 5: OVERVIEW MATCH PHASE BUDGET AND SPENDING

Planned FSTP budget	max. budget per beneficiary planned	max. budget per beneficiary actual	Actual FSTP budget	Balance
€ 280.000	€ 7.000	€ 4.000	€ 56.180	€ 223.819

2.4 KPI'S AND RESULTS

41 beneficiaries were selected and accepted the invitation to join the 1st Match phase of the STADIEM programme. And even with the ongoing Covid-19 crisis, the consortium managed to implement the Match phase successfully as a digital framework. All of the planned events and activities were organized and executed digitally, even the STADIEM Tour & Market Study was managed completely remote.

Out of the 41 start-ups/scale-ups that were accepted to the Match phase, a total of 37 start-ups/scale-ups managed to sign LOIs with relevant corporate partners throughout Europe, while all of the start-ups/scale-ups managed to generate new leads during the Match phase. Some start-ups/scale-ups even managed to secure LOIs with several corporate partners, and all the 37 start-ups/scale-ups with LOIs applied to proceed to the Develop phase.

2.5 DEVIATIONS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS

During the preparatory work prior to the start of WP4 and T4.1 Match in M09, the consortium recognized that the Match Phase would be challenging to efficiently effectuate in the planned period (June- July) due to the summer holidays. The Match Phase was therefore extended and was in effect from mid-May till mid-August 2021 to relieve the predicament of corporates being off work for large parts of the summer. The extra time was attained by shaving some time off the evaluation period from "Open Call End to Match" and "Match to Develop", and the Develop Phase. This way the programme in full would still be completed in line with the initial timeline.

Due to the ongoing Covid 19-pandemic and its related restrictions, all activities during the Match phase in the 1st cycle were executed online. This transfer of what was originally intended to be physical events to the virtual space, meant that the "Inspirational and Market Study Tour" in the Match Phase had to be executed digitally, with the start-ups/scale-ups taking a virtual tour of the innovation hubs to identify and connect with potential corporate partners. Each innovation hub facilitated this by organising virtual meetings, events, and workshops.

On the grounds of the restructuring of the Match Phase and Study Tour, the consortium decided not to bestow the start-ups/scale-ups the financial contribution of 7.000 € intended to cover costs related to travel and accommodation expenses during the Study Tour. As a substitute, each start-up/scale-up was allowed a financial contribution of 4.000 € to be reimbursed for training and upskilling activities completed in the Match Phase, which were relevant to the project execution, and which were pre-approved by their mother hub.

2.6 LEARNINGS

The short Match phase (two months) was scheduled right in the middle of the summer holidays. The timing of the phase made it extremely demanding for the hubs to engage their ecosystems during the STADIEM Tour & Market Study, especially since the start-ups/scale-ups and corporates had to meet remotely. Due to these conditions, the hubs found it increasingly hard to involve corporates, investors, and other stakeholders for each of the four rotation rounds during the tour. This left the 4th cohort at each of the hubs with less chances to sign an LOI from the 4th hub.

Having to implement the STADIEM programme virtually due to the impact from the Covid-19 Pandemic and its related restrictions, left both the start-ups/scale-ups and the STADIEM project with less visibility and impact with no chance of physical events during the Match phase. This also caused the start-ups/scale-ups and consortium with fewer opportunities to get to know each other.

At the end of the Match phase, we had more applications than anticipated, due to more start-ups/scale-ups managing to sign LOIs than expected. This made us experience that the evaluation and selection process from Match to Develop was less than ideal to manage all 37 applications, as the process was devised with fewer applications in mind. After the evaluation, six start-ups/scale-ups that didn't proceed to the Develop phase, appealed the decision. After reviewing each appeal and conferring with the legal team at VRT, none of the appeals was upheld as it was concluded that their claims were either incorrect or didn't hold cause to change the evaluation decision.

To bring the lessons learned from the 1st Match phase into action, we have recognized several improvement measures to implement for the 2nd Match Phase. In the upcoming Match phase, we have scheduled an earlier start, by starting in the very beginning of May 2022. In addition, it is decided to compress the phase down to the original two months, to finish the matchmaking before the summer holidays.

For the 2nd cycle, the rotation system will be changed in order to provide the best possible matches from all hubs' ecosystems. Instead of cohort by cohort, all start-ups/scale-ups will be invited to come together to one hub each week of the STADIEM Tour & Market Study. While visiting the hubs, they will be invited to participate in matchmaking events and training sessions organised by the hubs. Each innovation hub will be responsible to organise one attractive event, both for the start-ups/scale-ups and corporates/investors.

By having a four-week STADIEM Tour & Market Study, where we bring together all 40 start-ups/scale-ups, the corporates, investors, and other stakeholders, we anticipate that we will have the opportunity to create more impact for all involved parties. Each hub will still serve as the mother hub and main point of contact for their own cohort of 10 start-ups/scale-ups. Meanwhile, personal introductions will be offered by each hub throughout the Match Phase' duration, on top of the matchmaking events.

TABLE 6: TIMELINE OVER THE STADIEM TOUR & MARKET STUDY HUB ROTATION – 2ND CYCLE

2022	2/05/22	09-15/5	16-22/05	23-29/6	30/5-5/6	6-12/6	13/06-1/07	2-21/07
MCB cohort	Kick off	VRT Week in Brussels	NMA Week in Hamburg	ST week in Tallinn	Mid Terms	MCB week in Bergen	LOI / application	Selection
NMA cohort	Kick off				Mid Terms		LOI / application	Selection
ST cohort	Kick off				Mid Terms		LOI / application	Selection
VRT cohort	Kick off				Mid Terms		LOI / application	Selection

During the Match phase for the 2nd cycle, the evaluation and selection process is to be revised. F6S will take a leading role in the technical support and communication during the process.

We will keep the two existing steps of the process but combine the results from both steps for each start-up/scale-up, leaving us with a final score to select the proceeding teams by. It will be allocated four weeks for the process from Match to Develop, leaving two weeks for the external evaluators to assess and score all applications, one week for the Investment Committee meeting, the following ranking, consensus meeting, and informing the ones selected to proceed, and a final week before kicking off the Develop phase to receive signed contracts and send evaluation reports to all applicants. All start-ups/scale-ups in the Match Phase 2nd cycle will be invited to pitch at the final ICM.

3 DEVELOP PHASE

TABLE 7: OVERVIEW DEVELOP PHASE DETAILS

Task N°	Title	Lead	Contributing Partners	Timing
4.2	Develop	MCB	NMA, STK, VRT	M11-M28

3.1 DESCRIPTION AND OBJECTIVES

The Develop Phase is the second phase of the STADIEM programme, where at least 16 start-ups/scale-ups selected to the Match phase are invited to join following the Match phase evaluation and selection process. The objective of the Develop Phase is as stated in the Grant Agreement, Annex 1 (page. 22), the “*Development of the start-ups through the STADIEM methodology*”, where the main outcome is the “*delivery of the curriculum for media start-ups*”, supporting the start-ups/scale-ups while they co-develop their solutions together with their corporate partner.

In the 1st cycle, 16 start-ups/scale-ups were selected and invited to join the six-month Develop Phase. Each beneficiary can receive a maximum of € 70.000 in funding support from the STADIEM consortium in the Develop Phase. The Phase was kicked off with an onboarding meeting on 30 August 2021, with the final evaluation taking place during the ICM on 2 March 2022.

3.2 FRAMEWORK

3.2.1 Overview of Timeline

The Develop Phase was kicked off with an onboarding meeting where all 16 selected start-ups/scale-ups were invited to get a briefing of expected outcomes, processes and deadlines during the Develop Phase. The start-ups/scale-ups were then divided between the innovation hubs, which each was responsible for 4 start-ups/scale-ups best suited to the hubs’ expertise. The mother hubs assisted with coaching, follow-up, and served as the main point of contact for each start-up/scale-up throughout the entirety of the Phase. The main activity for the start-ups/scale-ups during this Phase was to develop their solutions in co-creation with their corporate partner(s).

Halfway through the Phase the consortium organised a mid-term review of the start-ups/scale-ups progress and results consisting of mid-term review meetings with the hubs, submission of a mid-term report, and a mid-term Investment Committee Meeting. In the final weeks of the Phase is the final evaluation period. Here, each start-up/scale-up meets with their mother hub for a final review meeting, they have a demo for the corporate and mother hub, the hubs meet with the corporate to get their insights, and finally on 2 March 2022, the final Investment Committee Meeting took place, where the 12 top-performing start-ups/scale-ups was to proceed to the Integrate Phase.

Throughout the Develop Phase, there were organised monthly upskilling sessions called Training Tuesdays, and monthly social events called Humans of STADIEM. In addition to this, the consortium organised several networking and showcasing events. The start-ups/scale-ups were invited to pitch and network at Future Week in Bergen, to exhibit at IBC in Amsterdam, to pitch at MCB Expo, and to have a Demo Day at the end of the phase. Due to Covid-19 restrictions, IBC and the Demo Day were cancelled.

TABLE 8: OVERVIEW OF DEVELOP PHASE EVALUATION AND SELECTION PROCESS ACTIVITIES

Date	Activity
30 August 2021	Onboarding
8 - 12 November 2021	Mid-term review meetings
17 November 2021	Mid-term Investment Committee Meeting
14 - 18 February 2022	Demo hub - beneficiary - corporate
21 - 25 February 2022	Meeting hub - corporate
21 - 25 February 2022	Final review meetings
2 March 2022	Final Investment Committee Meeting

TABLE 9: OVERVIEW OF NEED-BASED SUPPORT ACTIVITIES

Activity	Time	Description
Check-ins	By appointment	Individual check-in meetings between start-up and mother hub Depending on start-ups needs
Business introductions	By appointment	Demand-based + cross-hub approach
Investor meetings	By appointment	Demand-based + cross-hub approach

TABLE 10: OVERVIEW OF SHOWCASING AND NETWORKING ACTIVITIES

Date	Activity	Description
29 September 2021 Bergen, Norway	Mingling event	Networking event with the start-ups/scale-ups, the consortium, start-ups from MediaMotorEurope and stakeholders in the Norwegian media industry.
30 September 2021 Bergen, Norway	STADIEM Pitching Contest	Pitching contest during MCB Future Week. The STADIEM start-ups/scale-ups pitch their solution in front of a jury and audience, competing to win best pitch.
Cancelled due to Covid	IBC	The 16 start-ups were invited to exhibit at the STADIEM booth at the International Broadcasting Convention (IBC), the largest industry gathering in Europe.
3 December 2021 Online	MCB Expo	The Norwegian Media Cluster (MCB) organized a hybrid expo where the STADIEM consortium and two STADIEM start-ups/scale-ups presented.
Cancelled	Demo Day	Big splash event where 16 start-ups can demo their technology to an audience of corporates, investors, and other stakeholders

TABLE 11: OVERVIEW OF HUMANS OF STADIEM ACTIVITIES

Date	Activity	Description
24 September 2021	Activity cancelled as the next week, the Future Week would take place where start-ups/scale-ups and consortium partners could meet in real life	N/A
29 October 2021	You are the music in me	Start-ups/scale-ups and hubs were invited to send in their favorite song. During the get-together, we played all submitted songs and created a STADIEM playlist. The event resulted in a few interesting stories and exchanges.
26 November 2021	Crazy rant carousel	Participants were asked to share their little annoyances in life. This resulted in some very interesting inventions begging to be developed.
23 December 2021	Activity cancelled with the end-of-year rush the start-ups/scale-ups were experiencing	N/A
28 January 2022	Develop Final Countdown	This get-together was organised to have everyone in the same room in order to go over the different steps of the Develop Phase final steps and address questions and concerns
25 February 2022	Develop Closure Activity cancelled due to wishes from the start-ups who rather wished to focus on writing the Develop Phase final review report.	With this get-together, we want to take a moment to look back on the Develop Phase, share best and worst practices, and address questions and concerns about the final review report

TABLE 12: OVERVIEW OF TRAINING TUESDAY ACTIVITIES

Date	Topic	Organiser	Trainer
21 September 2021	How to prepare for a corporate collaboration from a business and legal perspective?	STK	
19 October 2021	Easy testing	NMA	Meinolf Ellers
16 November 2021	Corporate venturing	VRT	Omar Mohout
14 December 2021	Managing and preparing the pilot: aligning start-up and corporate expectations	STK	Sebastian Toupy
18 January 2022	Storytelling	MCB	Speaklab
8 February 2022	Ensuring a deployment framework: GDPR, SLA, certifications and beyond	STK	Andres Ojaver

3.2.2 Support and Follow-up

During the Develop Phase, each start-up/scale-up was assigned a mother hub, which throughout the phase assisted with coaching, follow-up, and served as the main point of contact for the start-up/scale-up. The mother hubs provided their start-ups with individual check-ins and follow up meetings based on the individual needs and wants of the start-up/scale-up. These meetings were additional to the mother hub and start-up/scale-up meetings part of the evaluation and selection process. In addition to the check-ins, the mother hubs also facilitated business and investor introductions with companies in their networks based on the needs for each start-up/scale-up.

TABLE 13: OVERVIEW OF DEVELOP NEED-BASED SUPPORT ACTIVITIES

Activity	Time	Description
Check-ins	By appointment	Individual check-in meetings between start-up and mother hub Depending on start-ups needs
Business introductions	By appointment	Demand-based + cross-hub approach
Investor meetings	By appointment	Demand-based + cross-hub approach

3.2.3 Networking and Showcasing Events

To promote the start-ups/scale-ups and in building the STADIEM community, showcasing, networking, and social activities was organised as part of the Develop Phase. The goal of the showcasing events was to create attention around the start-ups/scale-ups amongst relevant

At the start of the Phase, all the start-ups/scale-ups were invited to Bergen to join MCBs annual media and media tech festival: Future Week. Here, MCB organised an in-person pitching contest for the participating STADIEM start-ups/scale-ups, in front of an audience from the Norwegian media industry. A mingling event was also organised during the stay in Bergen, where the STADIEM start-ups/scale-ups, had the opportunity to network with each other, Norwegian media industry stakeholders, the STADIEM consortium, and start-ups from the MediaMotorEurope project.

The STADIEM consortium organised for the start-ups/scale-ups to exhibit at a STADIEM paid booth at the largest industry gathering in Europe: The International Broadcasting Convention (IBC). Due to the increasing numbers of Covid-infections in the hosting country, the Netherlands, IBC was cancelled by the event organiser a week before the event was supposed to take place. As a substitute to the convention, MCB hosted a hybrid event: MCB Expo, for their members and partners. Two of the STADIEM start-ups/scale-ups were invited here to present their solutions to the industry audience, the STADIEM consortium was also invited to present the launch of the project's 2nd Open Call.

As part of the framework, it was also planned to organise a Demo Day at the end of the Phase for the start-ups/scale-ups to demo their new solutions to an audience of corporates, investors, and other stakeholders. Due to the Covid situation, this event was also cancelled.

TABLE 14: OVERVIEW OF SHOWCASING AND NETWORKING ACTIVITIES

Date	Activity	Description
29 September 2021 Bergen, Norway	Mingling event	Networking event with the start-ups/scale-ups, the consortium, start-ups from MediaMotorEurope and stakeholders in the Norwegian media industry.
30 September 2021 Bergen, Norway	STADIEM Pitching Contest	Pitching contest during MCB Future Week. The STADIEM start-ups/scale-ups pitch their solution in front of a jury and audience, competing to win best pitch.
Cancelled due to Covid	IBC	The 16 start-ups were invited to exhibit at the STADIEM booth at the International Broadcasting Convention (IBC), the largest industry gathering in Europe.
3 December 2021 Online	MCB Expo	The Norwegian Media Cluster (MCB) organized a hybrid expo where the STADIEM consortium and two STADIEM start-ups/scale-ups presented.
Cancelled	Demo Day	Big splash event where 16 start-ups can demo their technology to an audience of corporates, investors, and other stakeholders

The Covid pandemic and restrictions imposed by local governments has left the STADIEM consortium and the start-ups/scale-ups with few arenas to get to know each other. To provide an opportunity to get to know each other as people, the meetings “Humans of STADIEM” was organised as part of the Develop Phase framework. These meetings were social events organised by VRT at the end of each month in the Phase. Here, the participants engaged in social activities with the goal to get to know one another better and to share one’s experiences in the programme.

TABLE 15: OVERVIEW OF HUMANS OF STADIEM ACTIVITIES

Date	Activity	Description
24 September 2021	Activity cancelled as the next week, the Future Week would take place where start-ups/scale-ups and consortium partners could meet in real life	N/A
29 October 2021	You are the music in me	Start-ups/scale-ups and hubs were invited to send in their favorite song. During the get-together, we played all submitted songs and created a STADIEM playlist. The event resulted in a few interesting stories and exchanges.
26 November 2021	Crazy rant carousel	Participants were asked to share their little annoyances in life. This resulted in some very interesting inventions begging to be developed.
23 December 2021	Activity cancelled with the end-of-year rush the start-ups/scale-ups were experiencing	N/A
28 January 2022	Develop Final Countdown	This get-together was organised to have everyone in the same room in order to go over the different steps of the Develop Phase final steps and address questions and concerns
25 February 2022	Develop Closure. Activity cancelled due to wishes from the start-ups who rather wished to focus on writing the Develop Phase final review report.	With this get-together, we want to take a moment to look back on the Develop Phase, share best and worst practices, and address questions and concerns about the final review report

3.2.4 Upskilling and Training

As part of the framework for the Develop Phase, several workshops and training sessions adapted to the needs and objectives of the start-ups/scale-ups were organised as part of the concept Training Tuesdays. Training Tuesdays consisted of monthly sessions, covering topics such as corporate venturing, easy testing and storytelling, delivered by experts on each topic

recruited from the innovation hubs' ecosystems. All start-ups/scale-ups in the Develop Phase were invited to join these sessions, and they could request additional workshops based on their needs. All sessions were executed remotely and recorded. The recordings of the sessions, and any additional material, were uploaded to a shared Google Drive where all start-ups/scale-ups could access them and watch/re-watch the sessions.

In addition to the Training Tuesdays, the start-ups/scale-ups were invited to engage in need-based training approved by their mother hub within their € 70.000 Develop Phase budgets.

TABLE 16: OVERVIEW OF TRAINING TUESDAY ACTIVITIES

Date	Topic	Organiser	Trainer
21 September 2021	How to prepare for a corporate collaboration from a business and legal perspective?	STK	
19 October 2021	Easy testing	NMA	Meinolf Ellers
16 November 2021	Corporate venturing	VRT	Omar Mohout
14 December 2021	Managing and preparing the pilot: aligning start-up and corporate expectations	STK	Sebastian Toupy
18 January 2022	Storytelling	MCB	Speaklab
8 February 2022	Ensuring a deployment framework: GDPR, SLA, certifications and beyond	STK	Andres Ojaver

3.2.5 Evaluation and Selection Process

The evaluation and selection process during the 1st Develop phase consists of a three-part process:

1. Evaluation of each start-ups/scale-ups eligibility for the 2nd instalment of the Develop phase funding
2. Evaluation of each start-ups/scale-ups eligibility for the 3rd instalment of the Develop phase funding
3. Evaluation and selection process deciding which start-ups/scale-ups will be invited to the Integrate Phase

To successfully accomplish the Develop Phase and qualify for the Integrate Phase, the following requirements should be fulfilled by each start-up/scale-up:

- Start-up/scale-up presents needs and action plan for the stage at the start of the Phase
- The solution meets the needs of the corporate (validated by the corporate)
- Corporate confirms dedicating resources to the pilot
- Corporate and start-up/scale-up identify KPIs
- Corporate confirms the likelihood of piloting (No likelihood of piloting =rejection from the programme)
- Start-up/scale-up defines the Budget funding/skill-up in next phase
- Strategy for converting a lead / leads to business (Start-up/scale-up)

TABLE 17: OVERVIEW OF DEVELOP PHASE EVALUATION AND SELECTION PROCESS ACTIVITIES

Date	Activity
30 August 2021	Onboarding
8 - 12 November 2021	Mid-term review meetings
17 November 2021	Mid-term Investment Committee Meeting
14 - 18 February 2022	Demo hub - beneficiary - corporate
21 - 25 February 2022	Meeting hub - corporate
21 - 25 February 2022	Final review meetings
2 March 2022	Final Investment Committee Meeting

All the evaluation and selection activities in the Develop Phase were executed remotely.

Halfway through the Develop Phase, the start-ups/scale-ups were subjected to a mid-term review consisting of a meeting, the submission of a mid-term review report, and a mid-term Investment Committee Meeting. The purpose of the mid-term review was to assess each start-ups/scale-ups progress thus far in the Develop Phase, and to determine if they were eligible for their 2nd instalment of the Develop Phase funding.

Between 8 and 12 November 2021, each start-up/scale-up met with their respective mother hub for a **mid-term review meeting**. The goal of these meetings was to challenge the start-ups/scale-ups on their progress compared to the project plans they submitted at the end of the Match Phase as part of the application to the Develop Phase. The meetings were an integral part in determining if each start-up/scale-up was eligible for their 2nd instalment of the Develop Phase funding. Before the meetings, each start-up/scale-up had to submit a draft of their **mid-term review report** (see template in Appendix B), and during the meeting the hub gave the start-up/scale-up feedback on the report in addition to following a predefined protocol of

questions, devised to ensure a coherent approach from all hubs. The final mid-term review report was due to be submitted on 15 November 2021.

On 17 November 2021, the start-ups/scale-ups were invited to pitch at the **mid-term Investment Committee Meeting**. During this meeting, the start-ups/scale-ups were allocated a slot of 15 minutes each, consisting of 5-10 minutes for their presentation on their progress thus far in the Develop Phase, and 5-10 minutes for questions from the Investment Committee members. Each start-up/scale-up's mother hub prepared lead questions for each start-up/scale-up, based on the conversation and outcomes of the mid-term review meetings. The questions delved into uncovered challenges and weaknesses, and more particularly on how the start-ups/scale-ups managed them during the first half of the Develop Phase. The Investment Committee consisted of three external experts from the Advisory Board (Anette Novak, Delphine De Wulf, Linn Dyveke Wilberg), and one representative from each of the four innovation hubs (Peter De Paepe (VRT), Einar Kaslegard (MCB), Tanja Deuerling (NMA), Sten Saluveer (Storytek).

In the mid-term Investment Committee presentations, the start-ups/scale-ups were to cover:

- Their progress on objectives and ambition
- Their progress on pathway to impact
- Their progress on implementation (timeline, budget,...)
- The work done by the corporate during the Develop phase

Like the mid-term review meeting, this mid-term Investment Committee Meeting does not contribute to the selection process of the Develop Phase, in deciding who proceeds to the Integrate Phase. The goal of this meeting was to get an overview of the start-ups/scale-ups progress thus far, their challenges, weaknesses, and successes to better coach them through the rest of the Phase.

The final weeks of the Develop Phase 1st cycle was set aside for the final three stages of the evaluation and selection process. The three stages consisted of:

1. 14 – 25 February 2022: The individual final review with meetings between the start-up/scale-up and their mother hub
2. 28 February: Submittal of the final review report
3. 14 – 25 February 2022: The corporate assessment, including a demo and meeting between the corporate and the hubs
4. 2 March 2022: the Investment Committee Meeting where the final evaluation and ranking will be made

The goal of the individual **final review meetings** is to challenge the start-ups/scale-ups on their progress compared to the project plans they submitted at the end of the Match Phase as part of the application to the Develop Phase. The meetings are an integral part in determining if each start-up/scale-up is eligible for their 3rd instalment of the Develop Phase funding. Like with the mid-term review meeting, there was devised a protocol of questions to be asked each

start-up/scale-up to ensure a coherent approach from the hubs. The final review meeting does not contribute to the selection process of the Develop Phase, in deciding who proceeds to the Integrate Phase. The start-ups/scale-ups are expected to turn in their draft for the **final review report** before the meeting, which was due to be submitted on 28 February 2022 at 10am.

For the **corporate assessment**, the goal was to determine from a corporate perspective if the start-ups/scale-ups have managed in developing a solution through the Phase that is eligible for integration. As such, the corporate assessment will be taken into account in the evaluation and selection process for deciding which of the start-ups/scale-ups will be invited to the Integrate Phase.

The set-up of the corporate assessment consisted of two parts: a product demo where the start-up/scale-up are to give a full hands-on demo of the developed solution and highlight how the solution results from a co-creative process, in front of the hub and the corporate, followed by a conversation between hub and corporate to assess how likely the corporate is to integrate the solution. During the hub-corporate meeting, the corporate partners are asked to score the start-ups/scale-ups between 1 and 5, where a score of 1 equals failed, and a score of 5 equals integratable.

On 2 March 2022, the end-of-phase **Investment Committee Meeting** took place. The goal of the Investment Committee Meeting is to determine which start-ups/scale-ups will be invited to proceed to the Integrate Phase. During this meeting, the start-ups/scale-ups were allocated a slot of 10 minutes each where they will give a final pitch highlighting the innovative solution they built, which corporate need it addresses and how it solves the corporate need. As in the previous Investment Committee Meetings, the committee will consist of three external experts from the Advisory Board (Anette Novak, Delphine De Wulf, Linn Dyveke Wilberg), and one representative from each of the four innovation hubs (Trees de Bruyne (VRT), Marianne Fjellhaug (MCB), Christoph Hüning (NMA), Tiphaine Vigniel (Storytek).

Each Investment Committee member scored the start-ups/scale-ups' pitches on the following four criteria:

1. The solution optimising, transforming or disrupting procedures, processes and/or workflows at the corporate
2. The problem the solution addresses within STADIEM and the (quantifiable) size of the problem for the corporate
3. The (quantifiable) value the solution provides and for whom within the corporate
4. The overall convincibility of the pitch

Each criterion was scored between 1 and 5, where a score of 1 equals fail, and a score of 5 equals excellent. The average scores of the pitches was cross-checked with the score given by the corporate partner during the corporate assessment before a final ranking was made. The 12 highest-scored start-ups/scale-ups of this ranking was on 3 March invited to the Integrate Phase, all of which accepted this invitation.

3.3 BUDGET AND REIMBURSEMENT

During the Develop Phase, it is budgeted that each of the 16 beneficiaries could receive a maximum of € 70.000, resulting in a total budget of € 1.120.000 for Third-Party Support Funding in this phase. As per the Sub-Grant Agreement, the up to € 70.000 in funding will be paid to the start-ups/scale-ups in three instalments: 30% at the start of the Phase, 35% mid-way through the Phase, and 35% at the end of the Phase.

When applying from Match to Develop, each start-up/scale-up had to submit a project plan and budget for the Develop Phase. This budget was the base of which the support instalments were calculated from. To receive their 1st instalment at the start of the phase on 21 September 2021, the 16 start-ups/scale-ups had to submit their updated Sub-Grant Agreement with a wet-ink signature. The start-ups/scale-ups each received 30% of their budget in this instalment, amounting to a maximum of 30% of the € 70.000 per start-up/scale-up. Due to some start-up/scale-up budgets being below € 70.000, the first payment to the beneficiaries amounted to € 335.130,50.

In order to determine if the start-ups/scale-ups were eligible for their 2nd instalment, the start-ups/scale-ups had to submit a financial statement along with their mid-term review report, in addition to participating in the mid-term review meeting and ICM. All 16 start-ups/scale-ups in the Develop Phase in the 1st cycle were determined eligible for their 2nd instalment. The total amount of funding paid to the beneficiaries in the 2nd instalment on 26 November 2021, was € 390.985,70.

To determine eligibility for the 3rd instalment, the start-ups/scale-ups had to update their mid-term review report with their progress thus far, in addition to a demo and final review meeting. The report and financial statement will then be reviewed by VRT and approved by the mother hubs by early March 2022. If all start-up/scale-ups prove eligible for this instalment, a forecasted payment of € 390.985,70 is to be paid in the 3rd instalment to the start-ups/scale-ups in March.

TABLE 18: OVERVIEW DEVELOP PHASE BUDGET AND PAYMENTS

	Payment 1 21 September 2021	Payment 2 26 November 2021	Payment 3 Foreseen March 2022
Budget division according to the GA and Third-Party Contract	€ 336.000,00	€ 329.000,00	€ 329.000,00 (forecast)
Total amount paid to the beneficiaries based on progress reports	€ 335.130,50	€ 390.985,70	€ 390.985,70 (forecast)
Difference	€ 869,40	€ 1014,30	€ 1014,30 (forecast)

3.4 KPI'S AND RESULTS

The Develop Phase's main KPI was the selection of at least 16 start-ups/scale-ups to start the Phase, and the readiness of at least 12 start-ups/scale-ups for the Integrate Phase. The first KPI was met, and the second KPI was also met when in early March the 12 top-performing start-ups/scale-ups were invited to join the Integrate Phase after the ICM and all accepted the invitation.

3.5 DEVIATIONS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS

The STADIEM programme was devised to consist of mainly in-person activities. Due to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, the majority of all Develop Phase activities in the 1st cycle have been executed successfully online. The only activities that have taken place in-person, were the STADIEM Pitching Contest and mingling event at the Future Week in Bergen in a room of somewhat lifted restrictions in September 2021. While we managed to organise these additional events to the original Develop Phase framework, the consortium decided to cancel the Demo Day planned at the end of the phase. The Demo Day was planned as an in-person event, and the format of the event couldn't be justly hosted as an online event while staying within budget.

3.6 LEARNINGS

In this report we have included some preliminary learnings from the ongoing Develop Phase for the 1st cycle. A full evaluation of the Develop Phase and implementation of improvements for the 2nd cycle is planned in March 2022, after concluding the Develop Phase of the 1st cycle.

During the STADIEM programme we've experienced that joint events have more impact than individual hub events or events including a cohort of start-ups/scale-ups, both compared to efforts of organising and the impact of the event itself. We have therefore recognized that both the consortium and start-ups/scale-ups can benefit from hosting more joint events in the next Develop Phase, and in the other phases of the programme.

We have also recognized a greater need to facilitate the generation of investor leads where necessary. Several of the companies in the 1st Develop phase are currently looking for funding, and the current Develop Framework has not sufficiently facilitated this particular need of these start-ups/scale-ups.

Many of the corporate partners collaborating with the Develop Phase beneficiaries have their first point of contact with the STADIEM consortium related to the corporate assessment (demo and hub-corporate meetings) in February 2022. As the Develop phase went on, there was an acknowledgement that the projects could potentially benefit from more feedback loops between the consortium and the corporate partners.

4 CONCLUSIONS

For the Match phase all planned activities, including the STADIEM Tour & Market Study were executed as online activities due to the Covid situation and travel restrictions. A total of 41 start-ups/scale-ups were invited to join the Phase, with 37 of them signing an LOI with a corporate partner and applying to join the Develop Phase at the end of the Match Phase.

The Match phase activities, including the STADIEM Tour & Market Study, planned for the 2nd cycle has been revised according to learnings from the 1st cycle. With the start-ups/scale-ups visiting each hub all together during the STADIEM Tour & Market Study, rather than alternating in cohorts through each hub. For the 2nd cycle, if the covid restrictions allow, the Tour & Market Study is planned as a physical tour with in-person events. The kick-off meeting for the 2nd cycle is still planned as a digital event. The two-step evaluation and selection process of the Match Phase is also to be revised, with the average score from both steps of the process making the final ranking, where the top 16 start-up/scale-ups will be selected to proceed to the Develop Phase.

During the Develop Phase for the 1st cycle, the majority of the activities were executed online. Apart from a couple of additional in-person showcasing events that had to be cancelled due to increasingly strict Covid restrictions, all planned activities in the Phase were executed, implementing a successful framework digitally. 16 start-ups/scale-ups were invited to join this phase.

The Develop Phase for the 1st cycle is in the final stages of completion. On 3 March, the 12 top-performing start-ups/scale-ups from the Develop Phase was invited to join the Integrate Phase, all of which accepted. The final decision on whether the start-ups/scale-ups are eligible for their third instalment in the phase will be taken at the start of March 2022 based on their final review report and accompanying financial statement. After the completion of the Develop Phase 1st cycle, the consortium will thoroughly evaluate the Phase and its activities to decide which measures to implement to better the experience for the 2nd cycle based on the learnings from the 1st.

APPENDIX A

**PROPOSAL TEMPLATE
FROM MATCH TO DEVELOP**

Closing date for proposals: 31 July 2021 at 17:00 CEST

Grant Agreement No.: 957321
Call: H2020-ICT-2018-2020
Topic: ICT-44-2020
Type of action: IA

WWW.STADIEM.EU

Proposal template: from Match to Develop

STADIEM

INSTRUCTIONSExpected results

Startup presents a needs, objectives and action plan at the end of the Phase upon which they will be assessed for the evaluation to the next Phase.

To successfully accomplish the Match phase and qualify for the Develop phase, the following requirements should be fulfilled by each start-up:

- The startup needs to match the overall eligibility criteria as set out in the Guide for Applicants.
- Startup presents its needs and action plan for the stage at the start of the Phase.
- Corporates evaluate the startup leads (max five questions).
- Budget for funding/upskilling in the Phase (Startup).
- Startup presents a strategy for qualifying leads.
- Startups who have already a signed LOI or another equivalent will be automatically scored higher for proceeding to the next Phase.

Stylistic requirements:

- **Delete the guidance text in blue in each section.**
- **Max. 5 pages for the sections 1 to 3. Not included in the page count are sections 4 to 7.**
- **Sections 1 to 3 and sections 5 to 7 are to be uploaded in the STADIEM Airtable by the deadline indicated above.**
- **Section 4 is to be completed in the STADIEM Airtable at two moments in time: halfway through the Match phase and by the deadline indicated above.**
- **Font Times New Roman.**
- **Min. font size 11.**
- **A4 format.**
- **All margins should be at least 25mm, not including headers or footers.**
- **Proposals should be submitted in PDF format.**

Proposal template: from Match to Develop

STADIEM

1 OBJECTIVES AND AMBITION

- **Briefly describe the objectives of your proposed work in the Develop phase. Explain briefly the core technology or product you want to pilot, the designated clients (particular or client types).**
- **Describe and explain the overall methodology, including the concepts, models and assumptions that underpin your work. Explain how this will enable you to deliver your objectives in the Develop phase, specifically regarding sales, growth and piloting. Specify any important challenges (in terms of workflows, tools, methodologies, knowledge, processes, team and so forth) you may have identified in the chosen methodology and how you intend to overcome them. Be as specific as possible.**

Proposal template: from Match to Develop

STADIEM

2 PATHWAY TO IMPACT

Describe the project's / action plan's main outcomes and give an indication of their scale and significance in relation to your growth in the Develop phase.

Describe the corporate or media organization you will be collaborating with and the nature / details of the collaboration. Who has been involved in the decision-making and how? Who will be taking on what tasks in relation to the proposed objectives, ambition and methodology? Does the project unlock value for the start-up and corporate and if so, how and what value?

Describe other partnerships you wish to pursue or consolidate during the project and what their added value is (e.g. how do you plan to utilize acquired knowledge, and resources from the consortium for other internal processes such as acquiring more clients, building VC connections and so forth).

Proposal template: from Match to Develop

STADIEM

3 IMPLEMENTATION

Provide a short and clear timeline / overview of the work plan, the timing of the different tasks using a Gantt chart or similar, a detailed work description, a list of deliverables / outcomes and a list of key milestones / KPIs. Provide enough quantitative detail to justify the proposed resources to be allocated so that progress can be monitored and understood by a relevant business executive from an industry that may or may not be familiar with your particular technological solution or product.

Provide an overview of the personnel efforts foreseen in the project. Who will be involved, what are their tasks and how will they be compensated?

Provide a clear and itemized budget plan. How will you spend the €70.000 that is foreseen for the Develop phase? Take into account that the reimbursement of costs depends on the deliverables and will be allocated against deliverables and milestones. Use a clear table.

Describe shortly your (project) management plan for the Develop phase. How will you set up the phase for successful completion? Provide a risk assessment and mitigation plan.

Give an overview of what training / workshops / events you would need that could help you reach your goals better / more efficiently and can be delivered by the STADIEM consortium members or third-party experts.

Describe the communication, marketing and outreach plan you will deploy during the Develop phase. Keep in mind that all communication activities about the project should correctly refer to STADIEM as European project accepted under the Horizon 2020 framework programme. All communication should mention the following, together with the project name.

Grant Agreement No.: 957321
Call: H2020-ICT-2018-2020
Topic: ICT-44-2020
Type of action: IA

4 KPI CHECKLIST

To be completed halfway through and at the end of the Match phase in the STADIEM Airtable.

TEAM

- How many team members are working on B2B sales / piloting in your start-up? Who are they and what is their position / role?
- How many team members are involved in the STADIEM programme? Who are they and what is their position / role?
- How many hours (eta) have they spent on the STADIEM programme in the Match phase and how many hours (eta) will they spend on the STADIEM programme in the Develop phase?

B2B SALES / ACQUIRING PILOTS

- What are your metrics for your B2B piloting strategy?
- How many new prospects have you acquired during the Match phase?
- How many leads did you generate for the pilot?
- How many sales activities have you completed (i.e. discovery calls, customer calls, sales, marketing activities, direct e-mails etc. - indicate by type and number)?
- How many hours has your team spent on acquiring the pilot customer?
- What is the customer acquisition cost for your designated pilot target?
- What channels and tools did you use for generating the pilot leads? What were the most effective channels?
- What is the churn rate for pilot customers?

PARTICIPATION IN THE STADIEM PROGRAMME

- How many STADIEM workshops / activities did you and your team attend? Give a detailed description.
- How many STADIEM match events did you attend? Which ones? Did they contribute to your planned activities during the Match phase and the preparation of the Develop phase?
- Which activities were the most relevant for your business / piloting processes?
- Did you utilize external experts/mentors/consultants (either suggested or outside of the consortium)? Who were they and how did they assist in unlocking new customers / pilots?

Proposal template: from Match to Develop

STADIEM

5 PITCH DECK OR OTHER PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL

Add the pitch deck or other promotional material you used to acquire corporate leads as an attachment.

Proposal template: from Match to Develop

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6 CORPORATE ASSESSMENT OF THE START-UP

To be completed by the corporate lead.

Does the proposed solution / collaboration unlock value for the corporate? If so, how?

Does the start-up clearly understand the needs and pain points of the corporate? If so, how? Has the startup done relevant research, identified the right stakeholders, and communicated those clearly? If so, describe.

Is the technology / solution proposed by the startup fit for the corporate either now or in the future and does it solve present, long-term or future pain points? If so, how?

Does the startup understand and address resources needed for the collaboration with the corporate (time, human, financial, technological) and does it propose solutions to commit or alleviate those? If so, how?

Contact person(s) within the designated corporate available for contact by the STADIEM consortium.

Proposal template: from Match to Develop

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7 LETTER OF INTENT / PROOF OF INTENT

An official Letter of Intent or written Proof of Intent by the corporate lead.

BUDGET TEMPLATE

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Type of action: IA

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Budget Template

STADIEM

Generic

Personnel costs	
Equipment	
Consumables	
Training	
Travel	
Subcontracting	
Total	

Detailed

	Month	Month	Month	Month	Month	Month
Personnel costs						
Equipment						
Consumables						
Training						
Travel						
Subcontracting						
Total						

APPENDIX B

PROGRESS REPORT TEMPLATE

DEVELOP PHASE

Periodic Technical Report
Periodic Financial Report

Start-up	
Key people	
Mother hub	
Period covered by the report	
Date of submission of the progress report	

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1 SUMMARY OF OBJECTIVES AND AMBITION

Give a summary of the work performed during the reporting period and main results achieved so far.

Give a prognosis of the work to be performed in the next reporting period and main results to be achieved.

Describe the innovation capacity you reached during the reporting period and the innovation capacity you foresee for the upcoming reporting period.

Periodic Reporting Template

STADIEM

2 SUMMARY OF PATHWAY TO IMPACT

Give a summary of the impact the develop phase has had on the start-up.

Give a summary of the impact the develop phase has had on the corporate.

Describe the collaboration with the corporate.

3 SUMMARY OF IMPLEMENTATION

Describe in detail the project management of the project during the reporting period.

- **Timeline**
- **Work plan**
- **Timing of different tasks**
- **Deliverables**
- **Milestones**
- **KPIs**
- **Personnel effort**
- **Budget (see template). Include an explanation on how the budget was spent. Explain any deviations between planned and actual costs. Justify subcontracting if there is any. Give an indication of in-kind contributions, from both the start-up and the corporate**
- **Risks and their mitigation**
- **Training / workshops / events**
- **Communication activities**

	Month	Month	Month
Personnel costs			
Equipment			
Consumables			
Training			
Travel			
Subcontracting			
Total			

4 CORPORATE ASSESSMENT

Start-up submits a statement from the corporate highlighting the work done by the corporate on the project, including an overall estimate of time commitment (meetings, co-creation workshops,...).

